

THE INNOVATIVE LEARNING NETWORK TO PROMOTE AND DEVELOP COMMUNITY ENTERPRISES, AGRICULTURAL TOURISM AND A NETWORK OF FARMER HOUSEWIVES TO HAVE COMPETENCIES ACCORDING TO THE KING'S PHILOSOPHY OF SAMUT SONGKHRAM PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this research are: 1) To study the conditions and problems of the implementation of agricultural tourism community enterprises and the network of farmers in Samut Songkhram Province in the management of human resource development of agricultural tourism community enterprises 2) To study the innovative elements of the development of community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province 3) To develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province. The population in this research was divided into 3 groups: the first group was a specific sample of volunteers, divided into 3 groups, 30 people, the second group is a member of the Agricultural Tourism Community Enterprises, Samut Songkhram Province, 250 people, and the third group was a group of luminaries, 5 people. The research tool was interviewed, and the questionnaire averaged an IOC value of 0.81 with a confidence value of 0.93 rather than 0.80. Data analysis uses exploratory component analysis, statistics, percentages, averages, standard deviations, and content analysis. The study found that 1) conditions and operational problems showed that there was no encouragement for personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises to develop their potential by participating in market activities, creating and developing traditional market activities in the community economy, online marketing versus offline marketing, and seeking market management approaches in the community economy according to King's Philosophy 2) There are 4 exploratory elements of innovation and 25 component attributes and 3) Innovation development has 4 processes: 1) Knowledge promotion along the lines of community economy according to King's Philosophy, 2) Promoting the organization of community economic practices according to King's Philosophy, 3) Promoting the Organization of Community Economics according to King's Philosophy, 3) Promoting the Organization of Community Economic Practices according to King's Philosophy, and 4) promoting the management of information technology in accordance with the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy. Satisfactory assessment of innovative development for training in marketers' courses, Agri-tourism community enterprises

and farmers' maid network, according to King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province. Overall average satisfaction is at the highest level.

Keywords: Human Resource Development / Community Enterprises / King's Philosophy

Introduction

The government has formulated a 20-year Thailand development strategy during 2017-2037. Under the concept of Thailand 4.0 or Thailand 4.0, community tourism and creative products, environmental and cultural conservation to promote creative production and empower local and community tourism, and competitive, stable and sustainable tourism. This is achieved in line with the country's goal of enabling Thailand to manage the high-value-added tourism chain in the global market and strengthen communities and society. As well as being a tourism owner who is critical to Thailand's economic and social development towards vision, stability, prosperity and sustainability (Ministry of Tourism and Sports, 2014: 1).

For the above reasons, it is an area of interest that will affect the development of the new generation of agricultural-minded people to know how to manage agriculture through innovation and modern technology. Able to build on entrepreneurship, self-reliance and local agricultural leadership. In the early stages, farmers would center and design self-learning (Suddhanom Tanchaen, 2016:1-3). This includes the implementation of research findings to propose ways to drive policy pushing innovation, learning networks to promote and develop agricultural tourism community enterprises to further strengthen community solidarity. This is because community solidarity is important and one of the indicators that will make community tourism, sustainable (Khanidda Kraisanti and Rasman Khamsri, 2016). It is also one of the elements that create the power to drive community development in all dimensions because it helps to work together towards the goals set by the community and gives rise to the power to move the community in the desired direction. As a result of sustainable community development, the panel recognized the importance of promoting community enterprises and developing community products. It truly studies the needs of executives and members of community enterprises. In addition, the needs of tourist customers are clearly in line with the government's policy of promoting tourism, major cities, and secondary cities for economic and social development at the local level. This is to develop good quality production, develop quality production activities according to the community way, and create marketing, agricultural products in the community have a king-based approach to sustainability.

Research Objectives

- 1) To study the conditions and problems of the implementation of agricultural tourism community enterprises and the network of farmers in Samut Songkhram Province in the management of human resource development of agricultural tourism community enterprises.
- 2) To study the innovative elements of the development of community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

3) To develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

Research Methodology

Population and Samples

Population is divided into 3 groups: the first group is a study of the condition and problems of the implementation of agricultural tourism community enterprises and the farmers' maid network, Samut Songkhram Province in the human resource development management of agricultural tourism community enterprises, i.e., a specific sample of volunteers joining the group, divided into 3 groups of 30 people. The second group is an analysis of the innovative elements of the development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and the network of farmers to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province, i.e. Members of agricultural tourism community enterprises, Samut Songkhram Province, 250 people. And the third group is the development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, 5 people.

Research Tools

Data collection tools include interviews, group discussions with environmental analysis methods, SECI Model analysis, and KM marketing tools. The survey averaged 25 IOC values equal to 0.80 and 25 total IOC values equal to 0.93 rather than 0.80. Confidence in Cronbach's method (Cronbach, 1990) is very high, and in-depth interviews are conducted with an individual-by-interview approach.

Data analysis

Data analysis from interview data, group discussions using content analysis, innovation element analysis using critical component analysis, exploratory component analysis statistics, and data analysis from suitability assessment using mean, standard deviation and content analysis.

Findings

Results of the study, conditions and problems, implementation of community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' maid network, Samut War province. To manage the human resource development of agricultural tourism community enterprises.

Conditions and operational problems It were found that there is no encouragement for personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises to develop their potential by participating in market activities, creating and developing traditional market activities in the community economy, online marketing and offline marketing, and seeking market management approaches in the community economy trajectory according to **The King's Philosophy**.

The results of the analysis of the innovative elements of the learning network towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and the farmers' network to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

Table 1: Data suitability checks

Questionnaire	Number of Questions (variables)	KMO	Bartlett's Test Sphericity		
			Approx. Chi-square	df	Sig.
Human Resource Development	25	.921	4875.565	300	.000

According to Table 1, the results of the data analysis analyzed the exploratory elements of learning network innovation towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, Samut War province. When examining the preliminary agreement, it was found that the correlation matrix of the 25 variables is not a unique matrix, that is, the 25 variables are sufficiently correlated to be able to continue the analysis of the elements. (Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square = 4875.565, df = 300, Sig. = .000) (Kalya Vanibunsha, 2013). When considering the individual variables, the overall sample selection adequacy (MSA) value was equal to .921, and the range of sample selection sufficiency (MSA) of the 25 variables was 0.99-0.90, which is greater than every 0.5 value, indicating that all the variables studied had sufficient correlations to be used for analysis.

Table 2: Statistical values after element extraction

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.092	48.367	48.367	12.092	48.367	48.367	5.432	21.726	21.726
2	2.212	8.848	57.216	2.212	8.848	57.216	5.011	20.044	41.771
3	1.388	5.553	62.769	1.388	5.553	62.769	4.262	17.048	58.819
4	1.072	4.287	67.055	1.072	4.287	67.055	2.059	8.237	67.055
5	.929	3.716	70.771						
6	.809	3.237	74.008						
...									
25	.098	.392	100.000						

According to Table 2, the analysis of the elements of the innovative variables of the learning network to promote and develop agricultural tourism community enterprises and the farmers' network to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to the

King’s Philosophy, Samut War province, found that a total of 25 variables, four important elements, were determined by considering the number of elements from Eigen values greater than 1.00 according to Kaiser's law, and the variability in the 25 variables could be explained in 67.055 percent. The results of the analysis of the elements when the axis is rotated by the varimax method. It was found that element 1 described variance of 21.726 percent, element 2 described variance of 41.771 percent, and element 3 described variance of 58.819 percent. The optimal number of elements is determined by the sequence in which the elements of the actual data with Eigenvalues are higher than the sequence of elements simulated by the program, resulting in the results of the analysis of 4 elements the researchers collected with exploratory factor analysis (EFA) of learning network innovations towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to the King’s Philosophy, Samut War province, there are 4 elements and 25 component attributes as follows: element 1 has 7 variables with element weight values greater than .20 with element weight values between 0.847 and 0.525, element 2 has 10 variables with element weight values greater than .20 with element weight values between 0.745 and 0.476, element 3 has 5 variables with element weight values greater than .20, with element weight values between 0.755 and 0.534, and element 4 has 3 variables with element weight values greater than .20 with element weight values between 0.749 and 0.655.

The results of the synthesis of data are then used to integrate the learning network innovations into the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy, according to The King’s Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province, with details of the results of the study and analysis of the basic data in each section, as shown in Figure 1.

There are 4 components and 25 methods of promoting human resource development capacity	Promoting knowledge in the community economy according to King's Philosophy
	Promoting community economic organizations based on King's Philosophy
	Promoting the work of personnel in the community economic landscape according to King's Philosophy
	Promoting information technology management in the direction of community economy according to King's Philosophy

Figure 1: The Innovative learning network to promote and develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and a network of farmer housewives to have competencies according to the King's Philosophy of Samut Songkhram Province

The development results of The Innovative learning network to promote and develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and a network of farmer housewives to have competencies according to the King's Philosophy of Samut Songkhram Province

There are 4 processes and 25 methods that can start from any previous step: 1) process on promoting knowledge according to the community economy according to the King's Philosophy, 2) process on promoting the organization according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, 3) process on promoting the competency of personnel in the profession according to the community economy according to the King's Philosophy, and 4) process on promoting the management of information technology according to the community economy according to the King's Philosophy. Satisfactory assessment of innovative development by key contributors 250 students for training on marketers course, community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' maid network according to King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province. Overall average satisfaction is at the highest level.

Discussion

The results of the development of The Innovative learning network to promote and develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and a network of farmer housewives to have competencies according to the King's Philosophy of Samut Songkhram Province are 4 processes: 1) promoting knowledge along the lines of the community economy according to King's Philosophy, namely, the development of learning processes resulting from study visits, the transfer of knowledge of community sages and luminaries, as well as the exchange of learning to generate income, create careers to strengthen community enterprises and farmers' networks, 2) promoting the organization is based on the science-based community economic trajectory, namely, the development of the leadership skills of the thought organization. Skills working with community enterprises and farmers' housewives network to produce and develop the production of agricultural products and services of community enterprises and farmers' housewives network better under the principles of King's Philosophy, 3) promoting the competence of personnel in the profession according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy is the condition in which personnel in community enterprises and the network of farmer housewives are loved. Faith and pride in being a community entrepreneur and a network of farmers. Attributes include honesty, patience, courage to change, creative initiative and ability to manage marketing and sales, strategic management, as well as embrace the King's Philosophy in living and working and 4) Promoting information technology management in accordance with the community economic trajectory according to The King's Philosophy, namely, managing the production of agricultural crops by using information technology for research, as well as marketing channels to promote market management and agricultural products and services of community enterprises and farmers' networks. They have knowledge and understanding of all stages of work, including work development, product development and problem solving of work problems for community enterprises and farmers' networks, building trust in the network's collaboration to achieve quality agricultural products and services that meet consumer acceptance standards. In line with Wutthichai Limorunothai (2019) has studied human resource management models for sustainable organizational development in the case of studying small and medium-sized enterprises in Bangkok and its vicinity in the current conditions where the environment is changing rapidly, technology is constantly advancing and evolving, managing the

organization's work to meet the needs of consumers in order to gain a competitive advantage requires a human resource management approach and an organizational development approach to be in line with the constantly changing situation in order to bring the organization into a balance between economy, society and environment, leading to the sustainability of the organization. The findings from the examination of structural relationship models for path analysis showed that human resource management, including talent management, good people management, and happiness management, affects organizational development and affects the sustainability of the organization. And in line with Swanson & Holton III (2009), it says that the core elements of human resource development are associated with learning development activities, the development of performance at both the individual and organizational levels, as well as the development of the organization as a whole, the human resource development process in the organization.

Suggestion

1. In terms of knowledge promotion along the lines of community-based economic trajectory should encourage community enterprises to encourage personnel in community enterprises to learn farming together with model farmers and community sages to develop knowledge, understanding and motivation to pursue agricultural careers. Community enterprises, encourage personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises to participate in studies from agricultural prototypes to be applied to generate income from the production and distribution of their own agricultural produce.
2. In terms of promoting the organization along the lines of community economics, according to the King's Philosophy, it should provide agricultural tourism community enterprises with personnel who can be guided or lecturers within the tourist destinations who have the knowledge and ability to provide information on agricultural tourism. Community enterprises of the conference to determine the aims. Role in creating businesses in the performance of tasks according to the competence and aptitude of personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises in the community economy according to King's Philosophy.
3. In terms of promoting the competence of personnel in the profession in accordance with the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, the agricultural tourism community enterprises should be able to transfer knowledge through the local wisdom of the community. An agricultural tourism community enterprise of having personnel who serve with a smile, a clear, polite and welcoming, friendly and warm welcome, familiar to tourists.
4. In terms of promoting information technology management in accordance with the community economy, according to the King's Philosophy, community enterprises should encourage the creation of new jobs. From the use of information technology in the community economy, according to the King's Philosophy.

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